

1 **VARIABILITY IN SUSCEPTIBILITY TO ANTHRACNOSE IN THE WORLD**
2 **COLLECTION OF OLIVE CULTIVARS OF CORDOBA (SPAIN)**

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14 **ABSTRACT**

15 Anthracnose of olive (*Olea europaea* ssp. *europaea* L.), caused by *Colletotrichum*
16 species, is a serious disease causing fruit rot and branch dieback, whose epidemics are
17 highly dependent on cultivar susceptibility and environmental conditions. Over a period
18 of 10 years, there have been three severe epidemics in Andalusia (southern Spain) that
19 allowed us to complete the assessment of the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba,
20 one of the most important cultivar collections worldwide. A total of 308 cultivars from
21 21 countries were evaluated, mainly Spain (174 cvs.), Syria (29 cvs.), Italy (20 cvs.),
22 Turkey (15 cvs.), and Greece (16 cvs.). Disease assessment was performed using a 0-10
23 rating scale, specially developed to estimate the incidence of symptomatic fruit in the tree
24 canopy. Also, the susceptibility of five reference cultivars was confirmed by artificial
25 inoculation. Because of the direct relationship between the maturity of the drupes and
26 their susceptibility to the pathogen, evaluations were performed at the end of fruit
27 ripening, which forced coupling assessments according to the maturity state of the trees.
28 By applying the cluster analysis to the 308 cultivars, these were classified as follows: 66

29 cvs. highly susceptible (21.4%), 83 cvs. susceptible (26.9%), 66 cvs. moderately
30 susceptible (21.4%), 61 cvs. resistant (19.1%), and 32 cvs. highly resistant (10.4%).
31 Representative cultivars of these five categories are ‘Ocal’, ‘Lechín de Sevilla’,
32 ‘Arbequina’, ‘Picual’, and ‘Frantoio’, respectively. With some exceptions, such as cvs.
33 Arbosana, Empeltre and Picual, most of the Spanish cultivars such as ‘Arbequina’,
34 ‘Cornicabra’, ‘Hojiblanca’, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Morisca’, ‘Picudo’, ‘Farga’, and
35 ‘Verdial de Huévar’ are included in the categories of moderately susceptible, susceptible
36 or highly susceptible. The susceptibility of cultivars was significantly correlated with
37 some fruit features such as size, lenticels, ripening, and some oil phenols, but these
38 correlations were weak. The phenotypic evaluation of anthracnose reaction is a limiting
39 factor for the selection of olive cultivars by farmers, technicians, and breeders.

40 **INTRODUCTION**

41 Olive (*Olea europaea* ssp. *europaea* L.) is the most extensively planted fruit crop in the
42 world, covering more than 10.2 million hectares of land, mainly in the Mediterranean
43 Basin. Almost 25% of the total olives are grown in Spain, where more than 45% of the
44 world’s olive oil is produced (FAO, 2015). Olive industry (oil and table) is a vital sector
45 of Spanish agro-food system with a total value of 3 billion euros, more than 385,000
46 agricultural holdings, and over half million of farmers (INE, 2015). In fact, the global
47 price of olive oil yearly depends on a large extent to the Spanish production.

48 Olive oil has numerous beneficial properties, mainly associated with its high content of
49 monounsaturated oleic acid (Espósito et al., 2004) albeit other minor components such as
50 phenolic compounds (i.e. hydroxytyrosol, oleocanthal, and squalene) have also shown
51 substantial benefits for consumer health (Beauchamp et al., 2005). For this reason, olive
52 oil consumption and, concomitantly the olive-growing surface, have notably increased

53 worldwide in recent years. Projects to expand the olive-growing surface affect new areas for
54 this crop such as different provinces of China, India, Saudi Arabia, or the States of Florida
55 and Hawaii in the USA. In many of these plantation areas, the adaptation of the different
56 olive cultivars and the pests and diseases of this crop are unknown. Fortunately, the
57 technicians and farmers have a broad range of cultivars that can be selected according to
58 their good adaptation to the target agro-environment area.

59 Olive was probably domesticated over 6,000 years ago in the Middle East, from which it
60 spread until covering the entire Mediterranean Basin. It is also accepted the existence of
61 other diversification centers across Mediterranean Basin (Besnard et al., 2013; Díez et al.,
62 2014). The first farmers selected the most outstanding individuals in each olive-growing
63 area according to their adaptation to the soil and climate and their agronomic characteristics.
64 These original cultivars were subsequently maintained by vegetative propagation and, in
65 general, have remained confined to small areas (Díez et al., 2015; Rallo et al., 2005). The
66 presence of homonymy (different cultivars with the same name in different zones),
67 synonymy (a given cultivar with various names in the areas that it occupies), and wrong
68 denominations is frequent in olive (Ganino et al., 2006; Trujillo et al., 2013). Thereafter,
69 the exact number of olive cultivars is unknown but it is likely that this number reaches
70 around 2000 (Bartolini et al., 1998). For this reason, and due to the absence of systematic
71 studies, there is a reduced classification of the olive cultivars according to their susceptibility
72 to many diseases, particularly in the case of anthracnose (Moral and Trapero, 2009).

73 Olive anthracnose, caused by the fungal complex species *Colletotrichum acutatum sensu*
74 *lato* (*s. lat.*), *C. boninense s. lat.*, and *C. gloeosporioides s. lat.* is the most destructive
75 disease of olive fruit and is widely distributed in many olive-growing regions of the world
76 (Cacciola et al., 2012; Martín and García-Figueres, 1999; Moral et al., 2014; Schena et
77 al., 2014; Talhinhos et al., 2005). About 13 *Colletotrichum* species, belonging to these

78 three complex species have been described affecting this crop (Chattaoui et al., 2016;
79 Schena et al., 2014; Talhinhos et al., 2005). In general, several *Colletotrichum* species
80 coexist in each olive-growing region being one dominant species and several secondary
81 (Moral et al., 2014; Schena et al., 2017). For example, the species *C. godetiae* (syn. *C.*
82 *clavatum*) is dominant in olive orchards of Greece, southern Italy, Montenegro, and
83 southern Spain albeit other minority species of *Colletotrichum* can be isolated from olive
84 growing in these regions (Cacciola et al., 2012; Faedda et al. 2011; Moral et al., 2014).

85 Olive anthracnose is also called soapy fruit due to its characteristic fruit-rot syndrome
86 with a profuse production of spores in a gelatinous matrix under wet conditions (Moral et
87 al., 2009). In addition to the direct losses due to the premature fall of affected fruits,
88 phytotoxins produced by the pathogen in the rotten fruits cause a second syndrome, the
89 dieback of shoots and branches (Ballio et al., 1969; Moral et al., 2009). Furthermore, even
90 with low fruit-rot incidence (5%), the olive oil coming from affected orchards shows poor
91 chemical and organoleptic characteristics that restrict or impose its commercialization as
92 extra virgin olive oil (Moral et al., 2014).

93 Both cultivar susceptibility and weather conditions profoundly influence on the olive
94 anthracnose severity (Moral and Trapero, 2012). For example, in the central provinces of
95 Andalusia, where the susceptible cultivars Hojiblanca and Picudo grow, severe epidemics
96 occur if the weather conditions are conducive during the autumn despite the farmers
97 typically applied a 2-3 copper-based fungicide treatments during this period. In southern
98 Portugal, where autumn-winter is more humid than in central Andalusia, severe
99 epidemics occur in super-high-density (hedgerow system) olive orchards planted with the
100 moderately susceptible cultivar Arbequina (Moral and Trapero, 2012; Moral et al., 2014).

101 Although satisfactory results controlling olive anthracnose can be obtained using inorganic
102 and organic fungicides, field application are not always effective for different reasons such
103 as: i) the number of registered pesticides in post-bloom is very small; ii) *Colletotrichum*
104 shows a high tolerance to copper, the basic ingredient of the main fungicides used; iii) and
105 the optimum period for fungicide application is relatively short (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral
106 et al., 2014; Roca et al., 2007). Since the unripe fruit are resistant to the pathogen, the use of
107 early harvesting before the drupe reaches full ripening or the selection of late-maturing
108 cultivars are efficient and environmentally friendly control measures (Moral et al., 2008).
109 However, these practices have some agronomical inconveniences: i) if the fruit is immature
110 (not completely black), it usually shows less oil content than mature fruit; ii) the immature
111 fruits show a high fruit retention force being difficult its mechanical harvest; and iii) when
112 the fruit still immature (green) during the winter, it is highly sensitive to frost damage (Rallo
113 et al., 2005). Therefore, the use of resistant olive cultivars to anthracnose is the most
114 effective control method, which does not present the previous inconvenience, and can be
115 combined with other measures such as biological and chemical methods or cultural practices
116 (Moral et al., 2008; Moral and Trapero, 2009; Preto et al., 2017).

117 The World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba (WOGBC) from Andalusia region,
118 southern Spain, is a magnificent setting to evaluate the susceptibility of the olive cultivars
119 to aerial diseases, including anthracnose, for several reasons: i) the WOGBC is currently
120 one of the largest olive germplasm bank with more than 900 accessions and 411 cultivars
121 from 24 countries (A. Belaj, *unpublished data*); ii) it is located in an endemic anthracnose
122 area (Moral et al., 2015); and iii) the whole group of olives of WOGBC has been
123 identified using Simple Sequence Repeats (SSR) markers, resolving the discrepancies due
124 to misidentification of the trees (Trujillo et al., 2013). During the last 10 years, we have
125 developed and validated laboratory and field methods to evaluate the susceptibility of

126 olive cultivars to anthracnose (Moral et al., 2008; Moral and Trapero, 2009). These
127 methods have been used to assess the resistance of traditional olive cultivars and new
128 ones, coming from the breeding program of the University of Córdoba (UCO) and the
129 Andalusian Institute for Research and Formation in Agriculture and Fishery (IFAPA)
130 (Moral and Trapero, 2009; Moral et al., 2015). While the disease reaction of some olive
131 cultivars is well-known (Moral and Trapero, 2009; Talhinas et al., 2015), most of
132 cultivars are still unclassified for their resistance to this pathogen (Moral et al., 2014).

133 Because the olive cultivars from WOGBC have not been systematically screened for
134 resistance to *Colletotrichum*, the objectives of this study were the following: i) to assess
135 the susceptibility of cultivars in the WOGBC to anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum*
136 spp.; ii) to identify cultivars representative of each of the susceptibility categories
137 determined in this study; and iii) to correlate the anthracnose susceptibility with other
138 phenotypic characteristics of cultivars. The phenotypic evaluation of disease reaction is a
139 limiting factor for the selection of olive cultivars by farmers, technicians, and breeders.

140 **MATERIALS AND METHOD**

141 **Plant material and orchard**

142 We have evaluated 308 accessions of cultivated olive from 22 countries of origin (Table
143 1). These accessions are conserved as a live collection in the WOGBC located in a 5.2-
144 ha flat and uniform field (37.51°N, 4.18°W, altitude 113 m) at the IFAPA, Center
145 “Alameda del Obispo”. The soil of the orchard was classified as a Typic Xerofluvent with
146 a sandy-loam texture, and the climatic conditions were typical of the Mediterranean area.
147 The experimental orchard is located \approx 1 Km from the main river of Andalucía,
148 Guadalquivir River, in a humid area where anthracnose is an endemic disease (Moral et
149 al., 2015). Because these accessions are fully authenticated by Trujillo and co-workers

150 (2013), we will refer to them as cultivars. The WOGBC was planted in several stages
151 starting in 1982 and currently contains more than 411 cultivars (A. Belaj, unpublic data;
152 Caballero et al., 2006). In this study, which covers the period 1997-2008, we present the
153 result of the evaluation 308 well-identified cultivars according to their reaction to the
154 pathogen. The remaining cultivars were not evaluated for different reasons (tree loss by
155 *Verticillium dahliae*, absence of yield, absence of replicated trees of the same cultivar,
156 etcetera). Each of the 308 evaluated cultivars has from two to 22 replicated trees randomly
157 distributed in the experimental plot.

158 The olives were planted in a 7×7 m square using one trunk per plant. The trees were
159 initially pruned to select three or four main branches to form the canopy structure: a free
160 open vase. After that, the olive trees were periodically pruned to renewal branches or to
161 eliminate death branches. The experimental orchard was irrigated during spring-summer
162 applying over 2000 m³ of water per year using drip irrigation. Bordeaux mixture
163 treatments (Caldo Bordelés Vallés, IQV, 6 kg Cu per ha) were applied during the spring
164 and autumn to control several fungal diseases and olive knot (Roca et al., 2007).

165 In previous studies, we identified the population of the pathogen in the WOGBC as *C.*
166 *acutatum* group A4 (Moral et al., 2015), which is the only group described in the central
167 provinces of Andalusia (Moral et al., 2014). The molecular group A4 was reclassified as
168 *C. clavatum species nova* (sp. nov.) by Faedda and co-workers (2011). However, Damm
169 and co-workers (2012) showed then that *C. clavatum* is synonym of the previous species
170 *C. godetiae*. Because the latter name is rarely used in non-etiology studies, we use *C.*
171 *acutatum* in the present article.

172 **Assessment of disease incidence in the field**

173 Fruit-rot incidence was assessed in each olive tree using a previously described and
 174 validated 0-10 rating scale (Moral and Trapero, 2009). The rating scale is the logistic
 175 transformation of the proportion of symptomatic fruits and it based on the sigmoidal
 176 equation:

$$177 \quad Y = \frac{100}{(1 + 3^{(7-X)})} \quad (1)$$

178 in which Y = percentage of affected fruit and X = scale value (0-10). The fruit-rot
 179 incidence data are normalized using this scale, and the scale values can be analyzed
 180 directly using parametric methods (Moral and Trapero, 2009; Table 2). When the olives
 181 showed a high percentage (> 5%) of symptomatic drupes, the assessor directly quantified
 182 the percentage of symptomatic fruits on the olive canopy. The percentage of affected fruit
 183 was then transformed in scaling rating values (0-10) rewriting the above equation as:

$$184 \quad X = 7 - \frac{\text{Ln}\left(\frac{100}{Y} - 1\right)}{\text{Ln}3} = 7 - \text{Log}_3\left(\frac{100}{Y} - 1\right) \quad (2)$$

185

186 Disease incidence was assessed at different times when most the fruits showed a value 4
 187 in the 0 to 4 rating scale (from green to black, respectively) for olive fruit ripening (Rallo
 188 et al., 2005). Disease incidence was assessed from mid-December to the end of January
 189 in 1997-98, 2005-06, and 2006-07 when severe epidemics of olive anthracnose occurred
 190 in the experimental orchard (Moral and Trapero, 2009). Data from low-level epidemic
 191 years were not considered because these data only divide the olive cultivars into two
 192 groups, the highly susceptible cultivars, which show a low-medium incidence of fruit rot,
 193 and the rest of cultivars showing no symptomatic fruit (Moral and Trapero, 2009; Xaviér,
 194 2009).

195 Because at the beginning of the spring 2007 there was an important pick of the branch
196 dieback syndrome after two epidemic years, we assessed this second syndrome according
197 to volume of olive canopy affected using the following rating scale: 0 < 10%, 1 = 10-
198 24%, 2 = 25-49%, 3 = 50-74%, 4 = 75-90%, and 5 = > 90% (Moral and Trapero, 2009).
199 In addition, we evaluated the presence of the pathogen on symptomatic tissues (leaves
200 and dieback shoots) by culturing small pieces on acidified Potato Dextrose Agar plus 100
201 mg of copper sulfate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) per liter (Moral et al., 2009) from May to August
202 during 2006 and 2007.

203 **Inoculation of detached fruit**

204 Green-yellowish fruits of five cultivars —‘Arbequina’, ‘Frantoio’, ‘Lechín de Sevilla’,
205 ‘Ocal’, and ‘Picual’— were collected at the onset of ripening from asymptomatic olives
206 in the experimental orchard during non-epidemic years. These reference cultivars were
207 selected by their well-known response to anthracnose in the field (Moral et al., 2014;
208 2015). The fruits were inoculated and incubated according to Moral and co-workers
209 (2008). Briefly, fruits were washed, disinfested, and sprayed with a conidial suspension
210 (10^5 conidia per ml or sterile water for the control) of isolate Col-104 of *C. acutatum* s.
211 *lat.* (formally *C. godetiae*). Inoculated and control fruits were incubated in humid
212 chambers (plastic containers) at 22-24°C under fluorescent lights (12 h alternant
213 photoperiod, $40 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). Disease severity was periodically assessed using a 0 to 5
214 rating scale where 0 = no visible symptoms, 1 = visible symptoms affecting less than 25%
215 of the fruit surface, 2 = 25-49%, 3 = 50-74%, 4 = 75-100%, and 5 = soapy fruit (Moral et
216 al., 2008). There were two replicates (moist chambers) per treatment and 25 fruits per
217 replicate arranged in a completely randomized design. The experiment was repeated once
218 and data analyses were performed on the pooled data from the two experiments.

219 **Relationship between resistance and phenotypic characteristics of the fruit**

220 Since some field observations and published data suggested a relationship for some
221 cultivars between susceptibility to anthracnose and some phenotypic characteristics, such
222 as size and phenol content of the fruit (Moral et al., 2014; 2015), we have studied these
223 possible relationships for some cultivars. To do this, the susceptibility of cultivars, as
224 measured by the average of fruit-rot incidence observed in the experimental orchard was
225 compared by Pearson correlation with published data concerning to agronomic
226 characteristics such as morphology, size, ripening, and phenols content of the fruit using
227 several databases (Barranco et al., 2000; Miho, 2015; Rallo et al., 2005; Bartolini and
228 Cerreti, 2017).

229 **Statistical analysis**

230 In other to estimate the phenotypic stability of the olive cultivar on anthracnose reaction
231 during the three studied seasons, we calculated the proportion of variability explained by
232 the cultivar, season, and the interaction cultivar-season. For that, analysis of variance
233 (ANOVA) was performed on the rating scale data of fruit-rot incidence of the cultivars,
234 which were evaluated during the three epidemic seasons with a representative number of
235 repetitions (at least two olive trees of the same cultivar). Subsequently, we calculated eta
236 squared (η^2) as the ratio the variability associated with an effect and the total variability
237 of our analysis ($\eta^2 = \frac{SS_{effect}}{SS_{Total}}$). Because η^2 overestimates the effect size, we also
238 calculated partial omega squared (ω^2) using the equation (Fritz et al., 2012):

239
$$\omega^2 = \frac{SS_{effect} - df_{effect} \times MS_{error}}{SS_{total} + MS_{error}} \quad (3)$$

240 in which SS = sum of squares, df = degrees of freedom, and MS = mean square. Likewise,
241 ANOVA was performed on the rating scale data of fruit-rot incidence and branch dieback
242 severity of the five reference cultivars.

243 In previous work, we have classified 18 cultivars into three categories of susceptibility
244 by comparing their reaction according to the disease response of moderately resistant
245 cultivar Arbequina (Moral et al., 2015). In this study, due to the high number of studied
246 cultivars and, for establishing groups more homogeneous according to their reaction to
247 the pathogen, the cultivars are classified roughly into five categories. These five
248 susceptibility categories were determined according to the reaction of the reference
249 cultivars Arbequina, Frantoio, Lechín de Sevilla, Ocal, and Picual, which were selected
250 by their well-known response to anthracnose under field conditions (Moral et al., 2005;
251 2014; 2015). Subsequently, a non-hierarchical K-Means cluster analysis with the initial
252 cluster center method under the assumption of five groups ($k = 5$, one group for each of
253 the reference cultivars) was applied to the classification of the whole of the cultivars using
254 the average value of the epidemic seasons due to it is the best parameter to discriminate
255 the susceptibility/resistance reaction of the cultivars (Moral and Trapero, 2009; Table 2).
256 The relationship between fruit-rot incidence and branch-dieback severity were analyzed
257 by the non-parametric Spearman rank correlation. A chi-squared test was used to check
258 if the country of origin of the cultivars had any effect on the frequency of resistant or
259 susceptible cultivars.

260 In the artificial inoculation test, disease severity values of inoculated fruit were used to
261 calculate a Disease Intensity Index (DII) using the following formula:

$$262 \quad DII = \frac{\sum n_i \times i}{5 \times N} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

263 where i represents the severity of symptoms (0 to 5), n_i is the number of fruits with the
264 severity of i , and N is the total number of evaluated fruit. For each cultivar and replication,
265 the standardized area under the disease progress curve (SAUDPC) was calculated by
266 trapezoidal integration of DII values over time expressed as a percentage of a maximum
267 theoretical curve. The SAUDPC was transformed to $\arcsin\sqrt{SAUDPC/100}$ when
268 necessary for homogeneity of variance. ANOVA was performed on the SAUDPC data,
269 and treatment means were compared using LSD test at $P = 0.05$. Finally, the relationships
270 between fruit-rot incidence and different agronomic characteristics (morphology, size,
271 ripening, phenols content, etc.) was studied by a Pearson's correlation test at $P < 0.05$.
272 Eta squared (η^2) and omega squared (ω^2) were computed in MS Excel (Microsoft,
273 Redmond, WA). Data from all experiments were analyzed using Statistix 9 (Analytical
274 Software, Tallahassee, FL) except K-Means Cluster Analysis that was conducted using
275 the SPSS 16 software.

276 **RESULTS**

277 **Susceptibility of cultivars in the field**

278 The incidence of fruit affected by *C. acutatum* on the trees of the WOGBC was evaluated
279 during three seasons (1997-98, 2005-06, and 2006-07) due to the low fruit-rot incidence
280 during the remaining years. Among these epidemic seasons, the most severe outbreak
281 occurred in 1997-98, whereas the lowest levels of the disease occurred in 2005-06. For
282 example, around 50% of the evaluated olive trees had a rating value scale ≥ 8 (i.e. median
283 ≈ 8) in 1997-98 and 2006-07, while the media value was around 5 in 2005-06 indicating
284 a higher degree of dispersion (Fig. 1). In the studied seasons, the fruit-rot incidence
285 greatly varied among cultivars and years. According to η^2 and ω^2 , the cultivar was the
286 most important factor explaining the total variance (approx. 60%) followed by the season

287 and the interaction genotype-season. In other words, the differences in severity of
288 symptoms among olive trees during the epidemic seasons were mainly due to the
289 genotype.

290 Because cultivar reaction to pathogen ranged continuously from highly susceptible to
291 highly resistant, we selected five cultivars across the susceptibility range. Each of the
292 selected cultivars was represented by at least five repetitions (trees) in the experimental
293 plot. These cultivars were: ‘Frantoio’ ($n = 8$ trees) for the Highly Resistant cultivars (HR,
294 0 to 2 in the rating scale), ‘Picual’ ($n = 8$ trees) for the Resistant cultivars (R, 2.1 to 4.3 in
295 the rating scale), ‘Arbequina’ ($n = 6$ trees) for the Moderately Susceptible cultivars (MS,
296 4.4 to 6.2 in the rating scale), ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ ($n = 5$ trees) for the Susceptible cultivars
297 (S, 6.3 to 7.9 in the rating scale), and ‘Ocal’ ($n = 21$ trees) as representative of the Highly
298 Susceptible cultivars (HS, > 8 on the rating scale). The fruit-rot incidence caused by *C.*
299 *acutatum* on the five selected cultivars varied significantly ($P < 0.05$) among them albeit
300 these differences depended on the year (Table 3). Concurrent with the greatest
301 anthracnose epidemic in 1997-98, we detected main differences among these cultivars
302 according to their anthracnose resistance. The cultivars Picual (R) and Arbequina (MS)
303 did not differ significantly from each other during the three epidemic seasons according
304 to the fruit-rot incidence, although the difference was significant when the analysis was
305 applied to the average fruit-rot incidence of the three seasons. Likewise, the branch-
306 dieback severity showed by reference cultivars differed significantly, being particularly
307 severe in ‘Ocal’ (Table 3). There was a significant and positive correlation (Spearman’s
308 correlation; $r = 0.691$, $P < 0.0001$) between the fruit-rot incidence and the branch-dieback
309 severity for these five cultivars.

310 Due to the large number of cultivars evaluated, the results showed a continuous gradation
311 in the susceptibility of cultivars ranging from completely resistant to extremely

312 susceptible. In other words, the resistance ranged from cultivars with none or very few
313 affected fruits (e.g. ‘Dolce Agogia’, ‘Frantoio’, ‘Grappolo’, or ‘Mavreya’), to cultivars
314 with all affected fruits (e.g. ‘Acebuchera’, ‘Picudo Blanco de Estepa’, or ‘Uovo
315 Piccione’). By applying the cluster analysis to the 308 olive cultivars, these were
316 classified as follows: 32 cvs. HR (10.4%), 61 cvs. R (19.8%), 66 cvs. MS (21.4%), 83
317 cvs. S (26.9%), and 66 cvs. HS (21.4%) (Table 1).

318 The frequency distribution of cultivars according to the categories of fruit-rot incidence
319 is skewed to the left (skew parameter $k = -0.436$) and had a negative kurtosis ($k_u = -$
320 0.694), which highlighted the prevalence of S or HS cultivars in the collection (Fig. 2).
321 Instead, the frequency distribution of cultivars according to the categories of branch-
322 dieback severity showed a positive skew ($k = 2.01$) and a positive kurtosis ($k_u = 4.907$)
323 due to most of cultivars did not show this second disease syndrome since it only occurred
324 in some cultivars that had a high fruit-rot incidence (Fig. 3). There was also a significant
325 correlation (Spearman rank correlation: $r = 0.530$, $P < 0.001$) between the fruit-rot
326 incidence and the branch-dieback severity for the whole of cultivars. This relationship
327 was weak albeit it improved when we only used the cultivars that showed a fruit-rot
328 incidence higher than 2.5 (0.71% of affected fruits). A simple exponential growth curve
329 was well fitted to the values of branch-dieback severity over fruit-rot incidence (Fig. 4).
330 Even so, some cultivars that showed high values of fruit-rot incidence did not present
331 branch dieback such as ‘Bouteillan’, ‘Grosal de Cieza’, ‘Imperial’, ‘Manzanilla de
332 Almería’, and ‘Picudo Blanco de Estepa’, which had an fruit-rot incidence > 9 but had no
333 dieback symptoms. On the other hand, the cv. Salonenque olive trees showed most of
334 their fruits affected by the pathogen (severity value = 9) and, also, a 50% branch-dieback
335 (severity value = 3) of their canopy affected by dieback of branches.

336 Comparisons for each country between the frequency of resistant cultivars (HR and R
337 categories) and the frequency of susceptible ones (MS, S, and HS categories) were
338 conducted to check if the origin of the cultivars had any effect on their susceptibility. The
339 null hypothesis in these tests was that there was no prevalence of any category of
340 susceptibility while the alternative hypothesis was, that there was a prevalence of resistant
341 or susceptible cultivars. Overall, there was a significant dominance of susceptible cultivar
342 for the whole of cultivars. Conversely, when the comparisons were conducted among
343 cultivars from the same country, there was no prevalence of resistant or susceptible
344 cultivars in most cases, probably due to the low number of cultivars available. However,
345 the susceptible cultivars were dominant in Spain and Syria while resistant ones were
346 prevalent in Italy (Table 4).

347 The pathogen *C. acutatum* was isolated from sampled leaves, shoots, and branches with
348 dieback symptoms albeit with a relatively low frequency (< 2.8%).

349 **Susceptibility of cultivars in artificial inoculation**

350 All inoculated cultivars developed typical anthracnose (soapy-rot) with significant
351 differences among them. None of the non-inoculated fruits showed disease symptoms due
352 to the absence of latent infection in the field. The first symptoms were observed in the
353 fruits of the cv. Ocal at 5 days after inoculation, while the fruits of the cv. Frantoio showed
354 the first symptoms 23 days after inoculation. Likewise, the pathogen caused the complete
355 rot (severity = 5) of the fruits of the cvs. Lechín de Sevilla and Ocal on 21 days, while it
356 needs more than 80 days to cause the completely rot of some of the fruits of the cv.
357 Frantoio. Many 'Frantoio' fruits still had no symptoms at the end of the experiment. The
358 SAUDPC analysis significantly separated the five inoculated cultivars (Fig. 5). Finally,

359 there was a significant correlation ($r = 0.989$, $P = 0.0015$) between the SAUDPC of
360 inoculated fruit and the fruit-rot incidence in the field.

361 **Relationship between fruit resistance and phenotypic characteristics of the fruit**

362 When we correlated the susceptibility of cultivars with several agronomic characteristics
363 of them, the correlation coefficients for most of the variables analyzed were not
364 significant ($P > 0.05$). Even the correlation between fruit-rot incidence in the WOGBC
365 and the observed susceptibility to anthracnose in different Italian fields was no significant
366 ($n = 28$, $r = 0.216$, $P = 0.269$). Conversely, the susceptibility of olive cultivars to
367 anthracnose was positively correlated with the fruit size ($n = 115$, $r = 0.403$, $P < 0.001$)
368 and the abundance of lenticels on fruit ($n = 52$, $r = 0.4439$, $P = 0.001$). In contrast, the
369 susceptibility of olive cultivars was negatively correlated ($n = 43$, $r = -0.325$, $P = 0.034$)
370 with the time of ripeness (i.e. the early-maturing cultivars frequently are more susceptible
371 than late-maturing cultivars), and the total phenols in oil ($n = 63$, $r = -0.257$, $P = 0.042$).

372 **DISCUSSION**

373 Here, we present the largest evaluation of olive cultivars for their resistance to
374 anthracnose, which is considered the most important fruit disease of this crop (Cacciola
375 et al., 2012; Moral et al., 2014). We evaluated the reaction of 308 well-identified cultivars
376 growing in the WOGBC during three epidemic seasons. Among others, two important
377 reasons for which the WOGBC is an excellent experimental plot to evaluate the resistance
378 to *C. acutatum* are: i) the plot is located in an endemic area for anthracnose due to the
379 proximity of the biggest Andalusian river; ii) the plot has an elevated number of HS olive
380 cultivars that act as an inoculum source of *Colletotrichum* (Moral et al., 2015). In a
381 previous evaluation, we presented a limited number of olive cultivars based on a single
382 observation (Moral et al., 2005) and without the correct identification of the trees using

383 molecular markers (Trujillo et al., 2013). In the latter study, Trujillo and co-workers
384 (2013) clarified numerous problems of homonymy, synonymy, and wrong denominations
385 in the WOGBC. For example, the original cultivars Arauco, Cañivano Blanco, Carrasqueño
386 de Lucena, and Razzola, which were planted in the WOGBC, have been identified as
387 synonymous of the cultivars Azapa, Picholine Marocaine, Picual, and Frantoio, respectively
388 (Trujillo et al., 2013).

389 All the cultivars were evaluated using a fruit-rot incidence rating scale that was previously
390 developed and validated (Moral and Trapero, 2009), although a few of them were also
391 evaluated according to the reaction of detached green-yellowish drupes inoculated with a
392 spore suspension of the pathogen (Moral et al., 2008; Talhinhos et al., 2015). The use of this
393 rating scale under field conditions to evaluate the cultivar reaction to the pathogen provides
394 an important (> 20-fold) economic saving respect to the artificial inoculation method (Moral,
395 2009). However, the correct evaluation of the olive cultivar under field conditions only can
396 be conducted during epidemic seasons (Moral and Trapero, 2009), which are sporadic in
397 Mediterranean conditions (Cacciola et al., 2012; Moral and Trapero, 2012). In our case, there
398 were only three epidemic seasons during a period of 10 years. In this study, the phenotypic
399 resistance of the cultivar was very stable, as shown by the fact that the experimental error
400 explained only around 10% of the total variance (η^2), while the cultivar genotype explained
401 over a 65% of this. This fact implies a high stability of the cultivar response to the
402 pathogen (resistance/susceptibility) during the epidemic years. The season and the
403 interaction cultivar-season had also a similar effect than that of the experimental error.
404 We did not conduct anthracnose evaluations during unepidemic seasons due to the almost
405 complete absence of the disease during these years, even so in the HS cultivars (Moral,
406 2009). In other words, anthracnose is a highly weather-dependent disease (Moral and
407 Trapero, 2012).

408 As it was previously described, the cultivar reaction to *Colletotrichum* is a continue
409 variable ranging from HR to HS cultivars (Moral et al., 2015). Nevertheless, the
410 susceptibility/resistance of the cultivars is more useful and easily understood by the
411 farmers and agronomist if the cultivars are placed into distinct ordinal classes (Pataky et
412 al., 2011). In this study, as in previous studies in olive diseases (Moral et al., 2005;
413 Trapero and López-Doncel, 2005), we classified the cultivars in five categorical groups
414 using a K-means analysis that minimized the variances. The intervals (the ranging values)
415 of each categorical group can shift slightly depending on the number of evaluated
416 cultivars since K-analysis uses a centroid value (average of the data of each group) for
417 each given categorical group (Jain et al., 1999).

418 In general, susceptible cultivars (MS, S, and HS, total 215 cultivars) were more prevalent
419 than resistant cultivars (R and HR, total 93 cultivars) regardless of country of origin,
420 except for Italy. For Italian cultivars, resistance was prevalent. One explanation for this
421 could be that many of the Italian cultivars in the WOGBC come from the north of this
422 country (Barranco et al., 2000; Bartolini and Cerreti, 2017), where favorable
423 environmental conditions for anthracnose are prevalent and, thereafter, the use of resistant
424 cultivars is essential to high-quality oils (Moral et al., 2014). The studied Italian cultivars
425 also show a high degree of genetic homogeneity, for example, all they belong to the
426 chlorotype group E1.1, except the S cultivar Carolea that belongs to the group E1.2
427 (Besnard et al., 2013). Likewise, all the Italian cultivars in the WOGBC, which belong to
428 the genetic cluster 2 described by Trujillo and co-workers (2013), are resistant to
429 anthracnose except ‘Cipressino’.

430 In the extremes of the resistance/susceptibility, we found the cultivar Dolce Agogia,
431 which showed a complete resistance to the pathogen (i.e. absence of disease symptoms),
432 and the cultivars Acebuchera, Picudo Blanco de Estepa, and Uovo Piccione, in which the

433 fruit-rot incidence was 100%. In this study, we described most of the evaluated cultivars
434 as susceptible (MS, S, or HS) to the pathogen, including the species *Olea ferruginea*,
435 which resulted moderately susceptible. For example, results of present study agree with
436 previous observations for susceptible cultivars: Ascolana tenera, Barnea, Galega vulgar,
437 Gordal sevillana, Hojiblanca, Manzanilla de Sevilla, Morisca, Ocal, Picudo, Sant
438 Agostino, and Verdial de Badajoz; and for the resistant or moderately resistant cultivars:
439 Bical de Castelo Branco, Coratina, Frantoio, Empeltre, Leccino, Manzanilla cacereña,
440 Mixani, and Picual (Barranco et al., 2000; Bartolini and Cerreti, 2017; Moral et al., 2015;
441 Rallo et al., 2005; Talhinhos et al., 2015). Conversely, the published response to
442 anthracnose of some cultivars does not match with our current results. In our study, four
443 of these cultivars ('Abou-Salt Mohazan', 'Azapa' [syn. 'Arauco'], 'Blanqueta', and
444 'Cordovil de Castelo Branco') were more susceptible and seven of them ('Arbequina',
445 'Cobrançosa', 'Itrana', 'Moraiolo', 'Morrut', and 'Picholine') were somewhat less
446 susceptible than their respective previous classification (Bartolini and Cerreti, 2017).

447 Errors in the classification of olive cultivars according to their resistance to anthracnose
448 have been extensively discussed by us and they are usually associated with: cultivar
449 misidentification, effect of the ripeness time during the evaluation moment, low inoculum
450 pressure, unfavorable environmental conditions for disease development, and confusion
451 with other fruit-rot diseases caused by species of *Alternaria*, *Botryosphaeria*, *Fusarium*,
452 or *Neofabraea* (Moral et al., 2008; Moral and Trapero, 2009; Moral et al., 2014; 2015).
453 Furthermore, the potential interaction between *Colletotrichum* species (or isolate) and the
454 olive cultivar needs a special mention. In general, this type of interaction has been
455 described with MS or S cultivars such as 'Galega vulgar', 'Cobrançosa', or 'Hojiblanca'.
456 Fortunately, R or HR cultivars such as 'Blanqueta', 'Picual', or 'Frantoio' show a high
457 degree of resistance to the different isolates (Talhinhos et al., 2015; Xaviér, 2009).

458 Concomitantly, some *Colletotrichum* species (or isolates) tend to be weakly (e.g. *C.*
459 *acutatum* s.str. or *C. rhombiforme*) or highly virulent (e. g. *C. godetiae* or *C. nymphaeae*)
460 against a broad range of olive cultivars (Schena et al., 2014; Talhinhos et al., 2015;
461 Xavier, 2009).

462 The histogram of resistance/susceptibility of the olive cultivars according to fruit-rot
463 incidence showed that data fitted a normal distribution but with a dominance of the
464 susceptible cultivars. Similarly, a substantial deviation from normal distribution among
465 cultivars for different agronomic characteristics has been described, such as yield,
466 ripening data, and oil content (Caballero et al., 2006; León et al., 2008; 2011). Although
467 our study was not intended to address the resistant mechanisms against the pathogen, it
468 suggests a complex and polygenic control of the resistance to *Colletotrichum* species. In
469 any case, other types of genetic control, including combinations of minor and major
470 genes, could be involved in the resistance of the olive to *Colletotrichum* species (Geffroy
471 et al., 2000). However, the case of major genes mediating the defense against non-
472 biotrophic pathogens is rare (Poland et al., 2009). In addition, phenolic compounds have
473 an important role in the defense of the fruits against fungal pathogen on different crops
474 (Prusky, 1996), including olive (Moral et al., 2015); in this case, and due to phenolic acids
475 derivate from different metabolic pathways in the plant (Boudet, 2007), there is not a
476 clear relationship between gen and any resistance compound. Fortunately for the olive
477 breeding programs, crosses between resistant cultivars produce a high frequency of
478 resistant descendants (Moral et al., 2015).

479 Likewise, important differences have been observed according to the severity of branch-
480 dieback among olive cultivars. This second syndrome of olive anthracnose is associated
481 with the production of phytotoxins by the pathogen on rotten fruits (Moral et al., 2009;
482 Moral et al., 2014). In our study, both fruit-rot incidence and branch-dieback severity

483 appear correlated albeit some of the cultivars, which showed high values of fruit-rot
484 incidence, did not show dieback symptoms. These results suggest differences in the
485 resistance mechanisms for both syndromes. In the experimental plot, the percentage of
486 isolation of *Colletotrichum* in semi-selective medium from symptomatic tissues of the
487 olive were relatively low (< 3%) during spring-summer and it was associated with the
488 rainfall events. Schena et al. (2017), using a duplex qPCR, have described a high
489 colonization of these vegetative tissues from May to October. In our conditions, we have
490 never observed fruiting bodies (acervuli) of the pathogen on leaves or shoots under field
491 conditions (Moral et al., 2009), although it can be induced in humid chamber after one
492 month of incubation (Moral et al., 2014). For this reason, we think that these tissues have
493 a limited role as inoculum sources in comparison with affected fruits in southern Spain
494 (Moral et al., 2014; Moral and Trapero, 2012). In contrast, acervuli of the pathogen have
495 been described on olive leaves in other countries such as Australia and Italy (Sergeeva et
496 al., 2008; Martelli, 1960). These differences could be due to variation among pathogen
497 populations, weather conditions, or cultivar resistance.

498 It is worth to note that the evaluation of the severity of branch-dieback caused by
499 *Colletotrichum* sp. may mislead the inexperienced evaluator since other pathogens can
500 cause similar symptoms. In the event of doubt, the evaluator should conduct isolation for
501 other candidate pathogens. For example, we diagnosed *Verticillium* wilt in more than 20
502 olive trees belonging to different cultivars in the WOGBC (Morello et al., 2016).

503 Although several morphological and agronomic characteristics of the olive fruit were
504 significantly correlated with the susceptibility to anthracnose in an outstanding number
505 of cultivars, the correlation coefficients were low, indicating a weak relationship between
506 the variables studied. In our study, total phenol contained in fruit was negatively
507 correlated with susceptibility to anthracnose as was previously described for a few

508 cultivars (Moral et al., 2015). Recently, Miho (2015) observed that total phenols of 78
509 monovarietal oils were not related ($r = -0.2971$, $P = 0.0530$) with the susceptibility to
510 anthracnose of these cultivars. However, he described a significant and negative
511 correlation with two of the 17 studied compounds: 3,4-DHPEA-EA ($r = -0.3522$, $P =$
512 0.0206) and p-HPEA ($r = -0.3522$, $P = 0.0360$). Using the classification of olive cultivars
513 according to their resistance to anthracnose provided Bartolini and Cerreti (2017) for the
514 28 in common with our study, there was no significant correlation both classifications.
515 This lack of correlation may be due to several factors that likely were not adequately
516 controlled in the work underlying the published data and that have been aforementioned.

517 Current trends in planting high-density orchards (which are very conducive for olive
518 anthracnose) and reducing the use of copper-based fungicides are contrary to the high-
519 quality oils demanded by consumers (Moral et al., 2012; 2014). Thereafter, the selection
520 of less susceptible cultivars to anthracnose is essential for new plantations. The
521 information about the resistance to olive anthracnose that is presented in this study is
522 fundamental for farmers, technicians, and breeders.

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530 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

531 Conceived and designed the study: AT and JM. Performed the evaluations under field
532 conditions: JM, JRV, LR. Curator of the WOGBC: JC. Performed the evaluations in
533 controlled conditions: JM. Analyzed the data: AT and JM. Wrote the paper: AT and JM.

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552 REFERENCES

- 553 Ballio, A., Bottalico, A., Bounocore, V., Carilli, A., Di Vittorio, V., and Graniti, A. (1969).
 554 Production and isolation of aspergillomarasin B (lycomarasmic acid) from cultures
 555 of *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* (*Gloeosporium olivarum*). *Phytopathol. Mediterr.*
 556 8, 187–196.
- 557 Barranco, D., Cimato, A., Fiorino, P., Rallo, L., Touzani, A., Castañeda, C., Serafini, E., and
 558 Trujillo, I. (2000). World catalogue of olive varieties. Madrid: International Olive Oil
 559 Council and Mundi-Prensa.
- 560 Bartolini, G., Prevost, G., Messeri, C., Carignani, G., and Menini, U. G. (1998). Olive
 561 germplasm. Cultivars and world-wide collections. Rome: FAO.
- 562 Bartolini, G. and Cerreti, S. (2017). Olive germplasm (*Olea europaea* L.)
 563 [<http://www.oleadb.it>].
- 564 Beauchamp, G. K., Keast, R. S. J., Morel, D., Lin, J., Pika, J., Han, Q., Lee, C. H., Smith, A.
 565 B., and Breslin, P. A. S. (2005). Phytochemistry: Ibuprofen-like activity in extra-
 566 virgin olive oil. *Nature* 437, 45–46. doi:10.1038/437045^a
- 567 Besnard, G., Khadari, B., Navascués, M., Fernández-Mazuecos, M., El Bakkali, A., Arrigo,
 568 N., Baali-Cherif, D., Bronzini de Caraffa, V., Santoni, S., Vargas, P., and Savolainen,
 569 V. (2013). The complex history of the olive tree: from Late Quaternary diversification
 570 of Mediterranean lineages to primary domestication in the northern Levant. *Proc. R.*
 571 *Soc. B.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.2833>.
- 572 Boudet, A. M. (2007). Evolution and current status of research in phenolic
 573 compounds. *Phytochem.* 68, 2722–
 574 2735. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2007.06.012>
- 575 Caballero, J. M., del Río, C., Barranco, D., and Trujillo, I. (2006). The olive world germplasm
 576 bank of Córdoba, Spain. *Olea* 25, 14–19.
- 577 Cacciola, S. O., Faedda, R., Sinatra, F., Agosteo, G. E., Schena, S., Frisullo, S., and Magnano
 578 di San Lio, G. (2012). Olive Anthracnose. *J. Plant Pathol.* 94, 29–44.
- 579 Chattaoui, M., Raya, M. C., Bouril, M., Moral, J., Perez-Rodriguez, M., Trapero, A.,
 580 Msallem, M., and Rhouma, A. (2016). Characterization of a *Colletotrichum*
 581 population causing anthracnose disease on Olive in northern Tunisia. *J. Appl.*
 582 *Microbiol.* 120, 1368–1381. doi: 10.1111/jam.13096
- 583 Damm, U., Cannon, P. F., Woudenberg, J. H. C., and Crous, P. W. (2012). The
 584 *Colletotrichum acutatum* species complex. *Stud. Mycol.* 73, 37–113.
 585 <http://dx.doi.org/10.3114/sim0010>
- 586 Díez, C. M., Moral, J., Cabello, D., Morello, P., Rallo, L., and Barranco, D. (2016). Cultivar
 587 and tree density as key factors in the long-term performance of super high-density
 588 olive orchards. *Front. Plant Sci.* 7, 1226. doi: [10.3389/fpls.2016.01226](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01226)
- 589 Díez, C. M., Trujillo, I., MartínezUrdiróz, N., Barranco, D., Rallo, L., Marfil, P., and Gaut,
 590 B. S. (2015). Olive domestication and diversification in the Mediterranean
 591 Basin. *New Phytologist*, 206, 436–447. doi: 10.1111/nph.13181

- 592 Espósito, K., Marfella, R., Ciotola, M., Di Palo, C., Giugliano, F., Giugliano, G., D'Armiento,
593 M., D'Andrea, F., and Giugliano, D. (2004). Effect of a Mediterranean-style diet on
594 endothelial dysfunction and markers of vascular inflammation in the metabolic
595 syndrome: a randomized trial. *JAMA* 292, 1440-1446. doi:10.1001/jama.292.12.1440
- 596 Faedda, R., Agosteo, G. E., Schena, L., Mosca, S., Frisullo, S., Magnano di San Lio, G., and
597 Cacciola, S. O. (2011). *Colletotrichum clavatum* sp. nov. identified as the causal agent
598 of olive Anthracnose in Italy. *Phytopathol. Medit.* 50, 283–302.
- 599 FAO. (2015). The FAO Statistical Database (FAOSTAT): Food and Agriculture
600 Organization of the United Nations [http://faostat.fao.org].
- 601 Fritz, C. O., Morris, P. E., and Richler, J. J. (2012). Effect size estimates: current use,
602 calculations, and interpretation. *J. Exp. Psychol.* 141, 2-18
603 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/a0024338>
- 604 Ganino, T., Bartolini, G., and Fabbri, A. (2006). The classification of olive germplasm. *J.*
605 *Hortic. Sci. Biotechnol.* 81, 319-334.
606 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14620316.2006.11512069>
- 607 Geffroy, V., Sévignac, M., De Oliveira, J. C., Fouilloux, G., Skroch, P., Thoquet, P., Gepts,
608 P., Langin, T., and Dron, M. (2000). Inheritance of partial resistance against
609 *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* in *Phaseolus vulgaris* and co-localization of
610 quantitative trait loci with genes involved in specific resistance. *MPMI* 13, 287–296.
611 DOI: 10.1094/MPMI.2000.13.3.287
- 612 INE. (2015). <http://www.ine.es>.
- 613 Jain, A. K., Murty, M. N., and Flynn, P. J. (1999). Data clustering: a review. *CSUR*, 31, 264-
614 323. doi>10.1145/331499.331504
- 615 León, L., Beltrán, G., Aguilera, M. P., Rallo, L., Barranco, D., and De la Rosa, R. (2011). Oil
616 composition of advanced selections from an olive breeding program. *Eur. J. Lipid*
617 *Sci. Technol.* 113, 870-875. DOI: 10.1002/ejlt.201000535
- 618 León, L., De la Rosa, R., Gracia, A., Barranco, D., and Rallo, L. (2008). Fatty acid
619 composition of advanced olive selections obtained by crossbreeding. *J. Sci. Food*
620 *Agric.* 88, 11921-1926. DOI: 10.1002/jsfa.3296
- 621 Martelli, G. P. (1960). Primo contributo alla conoscenza della biología di *Gloeosporium*
622 *olivarum* Alm. *Phytopathol. Medit.* 1, 31–43.
- 623 Martín, M. P., and García-Figueres, F. (1999). *Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C.*
624 *gloeosporioides* cause anthracnose on olives. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* 105: 733-741.
625 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/A:1008785703330>.
- 626 Miho, H. (2015). Variabilidad de la composición fenólica en aceite de oliva virgen de
627 diferentes variedades y su influencia en la resistencia a la Antracnosis (*Colletotrichum*
628 spp.). Master thesis. Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba, Spain.
- 629 Moral, J. 2009. Etiología, epidemiología, y resistencia varietal en la Antracnosis del olivo
630 causada por *Colletotrichum* spp. Ph.D. thesis. Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba,
631 Spain.
- 632 Moral, J., Alsalimiya, M., Roca, L. F., Díez, C., León, L., De la Rosa, R., Barranco, D., Rallo,
633 L., and Trapero, A. (2015). Relative susceptibility of new olive cultivars to *Spilocoaea*
634 *oleagina*, *Colletotrichum acutatum*, and *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*. *Plant*
635 *Dis.* 99, 58-64. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-04-14-0355-RE>

- 636Moral, J., and Trapero, A. (2009). Assessing the susceptibility of olive cultivars to
637 anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Plant Dis.* 93, 1028-1036.
638 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-93-10-1028>
- 639Moral, J., and Trapero, A. (2012). Mummified fruit as a source of inoculum and disease
640 dynamics of olive anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. *Phytopathology* 102,
641 982-989. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-12-11-0344>
- 642Moral, J., Ávila, A., López-Doncel, L. M., Alsalimiya, M., Oliveira, R., Gutiérrez, F.,
643 Navarro, N., Bouhmidi, K., Benali, A., Roca, L., and Trapero, A. (2005). Resistencia
644 a los Repilos de distintas variedades de olivo. *Vida Rural* 208, 34-40.
- 645Moral, J., Bouhmidi, K., and Trapero, A. (2008). Influence of fruit maturity, cultivar
646 susceptibility, and inoculation method on infection of olive fruit by *Colletotrichum*
647 *acutatum*. *Plant Dis.* 92, 1421-1426. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-92-10-1421>
- 648Moral, J., Jurado-Bello, J., Sánchez, M. I., De Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. (2012). Effect of
649 temperature, wetness duration, and planting density on olive anthracnose caused by
650 *Colletotrichum* spp. *Phytopathology* 102, 974-981. doi: 10.1094/PHYTO-12-11-
651 0343.
- 652Moral, J., Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. (2009). Elucidation of the disease cycle of olive
653 anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. *Phytopathology* 99, 548-556. doi:
654 10.1094/PHYTO-99-5-0548.
- 655Moral, J., Xaviér, C., Roca, L. F., Romero, J., Moreda, W., and Trapero, A. (2014). La
656 Antracnosis del olivo y su efecto en la calidad del aceite. *Grasas y Aceites* 65 (2),
657 e028. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3989/gya.110913>.
- 658Morello, P., Díez, C. M., Codes, M., Rallo, L., Barranco, D., Trapero, A., and Moral, J.
659 (2016). Sanitation of olive plants infected by *Verticillium dahliae* using heat
660 treatments. *Plant Pathol.* 65, 412-421. doi: 10.1111/ppa.12432
- 661Pataky, J. K., Williams II, M. M., Headrick, J. M., Nankam, C., du Toit L. J., and Michener,
662 P. M. (2011). Observations from a quarter century of evaluating reactions of sweet
663 corn hybrids in disease nurseries. *Plant Dis.* 95, 1402-1506.
664 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-03-11-0236>
- 665Poland, J. A., Balint-Kurti, P. J., Wisser, R. J., Pratt, R. C., and Nelson, R. J. (2009). Shades
666 of gray: the world of quantitative disease resistance. *Trends Plant Sci.*, 14, 21-29. doi:
667 10.1016/j.tplants.2008.10.006.
- 668Preto, G., Martins, F., Pereira, J. A., and Baptista, P. (2017). Fungal community in olive fruits
669 of cultivars with different susceptibilities to anthracnose and selection of isolates to
670 be used as biocontrol agents. *Biol. Control* 110, 1-9.
671 <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2017.03.011>
- 672Prusky, D. (1996). Pathogen quiescence in postharvest diseases. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 34,
673 413-434.
- 674Rallo, L., Barranco, D., Caballero, J. M., del Río, C., Martín, A., Tous, J., and Trujillo, I.
675 (2005). Variedades de Olivo en España. Madrid: Junta de Andalucía, M.A.P.A. and
676 Mundi-Prensa.
- 677Roca, L. F., Moral, J., Viruega, J. R., Ávila, A., Oliveira, R., and Trapero, A. (2007). Copper
678 fungicides in the control of olive diseases. *Olea* 26, 48-50.

- 679Schena, L., Abdelfattah, A., Mosca, S., Li Destri Nicosia, M. G., Agosteo, G. E., and
680 Cacciola, S. O. (2017). Quantitative detection of *Colletotrichum godetiae* and *C.*
681 *acutatum sensu stricto* in the phyllosphere and carposphere of olive during four
682 phenological phases. *Eur. J. Plant Pathol.* DOI 10.1007/s10658-017-1185-x
- 683Schena, L., Mosca, S., Cacciola, S. O., Faedda, R., Sanzani, S. M., Agosteo, G. E., Sergeeva,
684 V., and Magnano di San Lioa, G. (2014). Species of the *Colletotrichum*
685 *gloeosporioides* and *C. boninense* complexes associated with olive anthracnose. *Plant*
686 *Pathol.* 63, 437-446. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12110>.
- 687Sergeeva, V., Spooner-Hart, R., and Nair, N. G. (2008). First report of *Colletotrichum*
688 *acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* causing leaf spots of olives (*Olea europaea*) in
689 Australia. *Australas. Plant Dis. Not.* 3, 143–144. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1071/DN08055>.
- 690Talhinhas, P., Gonçalves, E., Sreenivasaprasad, S., and Oliveira, H. (2015). Virulence
691 diversity of anthracnose pathogens (*Colletotrichum acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides*
692 species complexes) on eight olive cultivars commonly grown in Portugal. *Eur. J.*
693 *Plant Pathol.* 142, 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10658-014-0590-7
- 694Talhinhas, P., Sreenivasaprasad, S., Neves-Martins, J., and Oliveira, H. (2005). Molecular
695 and phenotypic analyses reveal association of diverse *Colletotrichum acutatum*
696 groups and a low level of *C. gloeosporioides* with olive anthracnose. *Appl. Environ.*
697 *Microbiol.* 71, 2987-2998.
- 698Trapero, A., and López-Doncel, L. (2005). “Resistencia y susceptibilidad al Repilo” in
699 Variedades de Olivo en España, eds L. Rallo, D. Barranco, J. M. Caballero, C. del
700 Río, A. Martín, J. Tous, and I. Trujillo. (Madrid: Junta de Andalucía and Mundi-
701 Prensa), 323-328.
- 702Trujillo, I., Ojeda, M. A., Urdiroz, N. M., Potter, D., Barranco, D., Rallo, L., and Díez, C. M.
703 (2013). Identification of the Worldwide Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba (Spain)
704 using SSR and morphological markers. *Tree Genet. Genomes.* DOI 10.1007/s11295-
705 013-0671-3.
- 706Xaviér, C. (2009). Resistencia y grupos de virulencia en la Antracnosis del olivo causada por
707 *Colletotrichum* spp. Master thesis. Universidad de Córdoba, Córdoba, Spain.
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710 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

711 **Figure 1.** Box plots of fruit-rot incidence (0-10) caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* in
712 308 olive cultivars in the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba in three epidemic
713 seasons. Each box represents the distribution of fruit-rot incidence data according to
714 rating scale 0-10 (Moral and Trapero, 2009). The line within the box is the median. The
715 top and bottom lines of the box represent 25th and 75th percentile of the data. Lines
716 extending horizontally beyond the box represent the 5th and 95th percentiles.

717 **Figure 2.** Frequency distribution of fruit-rot incidence caused by *Colletotrichum*
718 *acutatum* in 308 olive cultivars in the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba (Spain)

719 **Figure 3.** Frequency distribution of branch dieback caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*
720 in 308 olive cultivars in the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba (Spain).

721 **Figure 4.** Relationship between fruit-rot incidence and branch-dieback severity caused
722 by *Colletotrichum acutatum* in olives of 308 cultivars in the World Olive Germplasm
723 Bank of Córdoba (Spain). Lines represent the fitted exponential growth equation $Y =$
724 $0.009 \times e^{0.492}$ and the confidential intervals at 95%.

725 **Figure 5.** Standard Area Under Disease Progress Curve (SAUDPC) of five reference
726 olive cultivars inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*. All the cultivars were
727 significantly different according to the Fisher's protected least significant difference
728 (LSD) test at $P = 0.05$

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Table 2. Rating scale values, average, and interval of percentage of olive fruit affected by anthracnose

Scale value (0-10)	Description	Average (Interval [%]^a)	Range
0	Affected fruits no observed	<0.04	0.04
1	From one to three affected fruits per olive tree	0.14 (0.04^b-0.23)	0.19
2	From one to three affected fruits per each quadrant of the tree canopy	0.41 (0.24-0.70)	0.46
3	From four to nine affected fruits per each quadrant of the tree canopy	1.22 (0.71-2.09)	1.38
4	Affected fruit easily detected (from 20 to 36 affected fruits per each half of the tree canopy)	3.57 (2.10-6.02)	3.92
5	Direct quantification of affected fruit	10 (6.03-16.13)	10.1
6	Direct quantification of affected fruit	25 (16.14-36.60)	20.46
7	Direct quantification of affected fruit	50 (36.61-63.39)	26.78
8	Direct quantification of affected fruit	75 (63.40-83.86)	20.46
9	Direct quantification of affected fruit	90 (83.87-93.97)	10.1
10	Less than 36 asymptomatic fruits per each half of the tree canopy	97 (93.98-100)	3.92

^aValues taken from the logistic function $Y = \frac{100}{1 + 3^{(7-X)}}$ in which Y = percentage of affected fruit and X = scale value.

^bDetection limit of visual assessments in the field (one affected fruit from 2,500 observed fruit per tree) (Moral and Trapero 2009).

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Table 3. Incidence of anthracnose in five olive cultivars in the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba during 1997-98, 2005-06 and 2006-07 742

Cultivar	Fruit-rot incidence (0-10)			Mean	Branch dieback (0-5)
	1997-98	2005-06	2006-07		(2007) 744
Frantoio	0.1 d ^a	0.0 d	0.1 d	0.1 e	0.0 c 745
Picual	3.5 c	1.0 c	4.7 c	3.4 d	0.0 c
Arbequina	4.5 c	3.7 bc	5.5 c	4.9 c	0.14 b 746
Lechín de Sevilla	8.3 b	5.3 b	7.1 b	7.0 b	0.17 b 747
Ocal	9.9 a	7.7 a	9.6 a	9.2 a	1.38 a
Mean	6.5	5.1	6.1	5.7	748

^aFruit-rot incidence was estimated using a 1-10 rating scale in which binary data (proportion of affected fruit) are normalized by applying the logit 749 transformation of proportion. Scale values were directly subjected to analysis of variance and mean comparison tests.

Means with the same letter are not significantly different according to the 750 Fisher's protected LSD test at $P = 0.05$.

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Table 4. Origin, age and susceptibility to anthracnosis of the olive cultivars evaluated in the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba (Spain)

ORIGIN	Cultivars (No)	HR ^a	R	MS	S	HS	<i>P</i> -value ^b	R/S ^c
ALBANIA	7	2	2	3	0	0	0.3103	-
ALGERIA	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.2632	-
CHILE	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.4449	-
CROATIA	7	2	1	3	1	0	0.5480	-
CYPRUS	2	1	1	0	0	0	0.1136	-
EGYPT	3	1	1	1	0	0	0.3539	-
FRANCE	7	0	1	2	1	3	0.1693	-
GREECE	16	3	2	4	5	2	0.2752	-
IRAN	4	0	3	1	0	0	0.1758	-
ISRAEL	2	0	0	1	0	1	0.2800	-
ITALY	20	9	5	1	3	2	0.0082	R
LEBANON	2	1	1	0	0	0	0.1136	-
MEXICO	2	0	1	0	1	0	0.6850	-
MOROCCO	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.2632	-
PAKISTAN	1	0	0	1	0	0	0.4449	-
PORTUGAL	6	0	0	3	3	0	0.0613	-
SPAIN	174	9	28	34	55	48	0.0000	S
SYRIA	29	1	5	6	11	6	0.0249	S
TUNISIA	6	2	2	0	0	2	0.1898	-
TURKEY	15	1	6	4	3	1	0.3284	-
USA	2	0	0	2	0	0	0.2800	-
TOTAL	308	32	61	66	83	66	0.0000	S

^aHR = highly resistant (0 – 2 in the 0–10 rating scale), R = resistant (2.1 – 4.3), MS = intermediate (4.4 – 6.2), S = susceptible (6.3 – 7.9), and HS = highly susceptible (8 – 10).

^b*P*-value of the chi-square test used to determine the dominance or non-dominance of resistant or susceptible cultivars.

^cR = dominance of resistant cultivars, S = dominance of susceptible cultivars. - = no dominance of resistant or susceptible cultivars.

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Table 1. Reaction of olive cultivars to anthracnose, caused by <i>Colletotrichum acutatum</i> in the World Olive Germplasm Bank of Córdoba (Spain)		
Reaction	No	Cultivar
Highly Susceptible (HS)	66	Abbadi, Acebuchera, Adkam, Agouromanakolia, Azapa, Bolvino, Borriolenca, Bouteillan, Cañivano Negro-55, Chalchali, Chorruo de Castro del Río, Corbella, Cornicabra de Mérida, Dulzal de Carmona, Farga, Forastera de Tortosa, Fulla de Salze, Gatuno, Gerboui, Gordal Sevillana, Grosal de Cieza, Habichuelero de Baena, Hojiblanca, Imperial, Imperial de Jaén, Jabaluna, Jaropo, Limoncillo, Llorón de Atarfe, Loaime, Lucio, Lucques, Machorrón, Mahati-1010, Manzanilla de Almería, Manzanillera de Huércal, Manzanillo de Cabra, Merhavia, Meski, Morisca, Morisca de Mancor, Negrillo de Iznalloz, Negrillo de la Carlota, Negrillo Redondo, Nevadillo de Santisteban del Puerto, Nevado Azul, Ocal , Ocal-25, Ojo de Liebre, Palomar, Pavo, Picudo, Picudo Blanco de Estepa, Rachati, Rechino, Safrawi, Salgar Redondo, Salonenque, Sant Agostino, Sayfi, Sevillana de Abla, Sevillena, Temprano, Uovo di Piccione, Uslu, and Verdial de Cádiz.
Susceptible (S)	83	Abbadi Abou Gabra-84, Abbadi Shalal, Abou Kanani, Adramitini, Alameño Blanco, Alameño de Cabra, Alameño de Montilla, Amargoso, Amygdalolia Nana, Argudell, Ascolana Tenera, Asnal, Ayvalik, Barri, Blanqueta, Carolea, Castellana, Chorreao de Montefrío, Cipressino, Cirujal, Cordobés de Arroyo de la luz, Cordovil de Castelo Branco, Cornezuelo de Jaén, Cornicabra, Doebli, Dulzal, Escarabajillo, Escarabajuelo de Atarfe, Escarabajuelo de Posadas, Figueretes, Galega Vulgar, Gemlik, Gordal de Granada, Gordal de Hellín, Gordal de Vélez Rubio, Grosal Vimbodí, Izmir Sofralik, Jlot-841, Kaesi, Kalamon, Kolybada, Lechín de Sevilla , Lentisca, Levantinka, Macho de Jaén, Mahati-846, Manzanilla de Piedra Buena, Manzanilla de Agua, Manzanilla de Sevilla, Manzanilla Prieta, Mastoidis, Mawi, Mollar Basto, Mollar de Cieza, Morona Negral de Sabiñan, Negrillo de Estepa, Negro del Carpio, Nevadillo Blanco de Jaén, Nevado Basto, Nevado Rizado, Olivo de Mancha Real, Pajarero, Perafort, Pico Limón de Grazalema, Picual de Almería, Polinizador, Racimal, Shami, Sorani, Tempranillo de Yeste, Torcio de Huelma, Toruno, Varudo, Vera, Verdal de Manresa, Verdala, Verdale, Verde Verdelho, Verdial de Badajoz, Verdial de Huévar, Verdiell, and Zarza.
Moderately Susceptible (MS)	66	Abou Satl Mohazam, Arbequina , Arroniz, Azulejo, Barnea, Beyaz Yaglik, Bodoquera, Caballo, Cañivano Negro, Carrasquenho de Elvas, Carrasqueño de Alcaudete, Carrasqueño de la Sierra, Carrasquillo, Cerezuela, Changlot Real, Chorruo, Çobrancosa, Cordovil de Serpa, Cornicabra de Jerez, Cornicabra-1, Domat, Dwarf D, Erbek Yaglik, Escarabajuelo de Úbeda, Gaydoyrelia, Genovesa, Habichuelero de Grazalema, Itrana, Kelb et Ter, Khashabi, Kiraz, Klon-14-1081-1, Klon-14-1081-2, Konservolia, Lastovka, Lechín de Granada, Maarri, Majhol-1059, Manzanilla Cacereña, Manzanilla de Abla, Manzanilla del Piquito, Mari, Masabi, Mission, Moojeski, Morrut, Myrtolia, Negrillo de Arjona, Oblica, <i>Olea ferruginea</i> , Olivo de Maura, Picholine, Plementa Bjelica, Pulazeqin, Rapasayo, Redondilla de Logroño, Reixonenca, Royal de Calatayud, Royal de Cazorla, Royal de Sabiñan, Sabatera, Sandalio, Tanche, Toffahi, Valanolia, Villalonga, and Vinyols.

Resistant (R)	61	Abbadi Abou Gabra-10, Acebuche de Caravaca, Alfafara, Aloreña de Iznalloz, Arbosana, Athalassa, Beladi, Belluti, Bent al Kadi, Biancolilla, Bical, Buga, Buidiego, Canetera, Carrasqueño de Jumilla, Carrasqueño de Porcuna, Chalkidikis, Chemlal de Kabilye, Chemlali, Chetoui, Coratina, Corralones de Andújar, Curivell, Datilero, Dokkar, Dolce, Elmacik, Enagua de Arenas, Fishomi, Grit Eytini, Grossanne-67, Joanenca, Kalokerida, Kotruvsi, Leccino, Llumeta, Majhol-1013, Majhol-152, Manzanilla de Hellín, Manzanilla de Montefrío, Manzanilla de San Vicente, Maurino, Memecik, Mixani, Moraiolo, Patronet, Pecosó, Picholine Marocaine, Pico Limón, Picual , Real Sevillana, Redondilla de Grazalema, Sevillano de Jumilla, Shengue, Sinop, Sollana, Vallesa, Vaneta, Verdial de Vélez-Málaga, Zaity, and Zard.
Highly Resistant (HR)	32	Ayrouni, Azul, Bosana, Callosina, Caninese, Crnica, Dolce Agogia, Empeltre, Frantoio , Frantoio A. Corsini, Grappolo, Istarska Bjelica, Kan Çelebi, Kato Drys, Koroneiki, Mavreya, Megaritiki, Menya, Ouslati, Pendolino, Pequeña de Casas Ibañez, Perillo de Jaén, Piñonera-76, Racimal de Jaén, Rosciola, Royal de Calatayud-4, Selvatico, Toffahi-1000, Ulliri i Bardhe i Ti, Ulliri i Kuq, Wardan, and Zalmati.